

SITE SPHINX (EST)	DATE 11/19/80	AREA EAST SPHINX TEMPLE	SQUARE	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.39 - 10.41	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:	Width: ^{Starting Pit} 1.50	Length: ^{Starting Pit} 1.60	Depth: ^{Starting Pit} 1.70	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	SAND	TAN	LOOSE	Quartz SAND	T ✓ <small>See Basket Account</small>	Lm ✓ <small>scattered frags</small>	Gp
					D ✓	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
		A1 2 LARGE FRAGS		Other			
2 5-10m	SAND WATER Limestone Frag.	TAN	VERY LOOSE		T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
		A1		Other			
3 7m.	SAND SLURRY Limestone Frag. Granite Frag (few)				T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
		A1		Other			
4 14/19/80 15/19/80 ≈ 9-10m.	Limestone Frag. w greyish -black tint.				T / small ND. Sherd (RW) ??	Lm ✓	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
		A1		Other			
5 12-15m.	Grey (light grey on drying) CLAY				T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
		A1		Other			

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan:	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: 11/19/80 Drill Rig set up in area east of Sphinx Temple, about 20 m. E and few ms. S of SE corner of Square NI-E9-10. A pit for anchoring the rig 1.50 x 1.60 was dug to a depth of 1.70 ms. This went thru slightly grey loose sand to clean tan loose sand w/ scattered limestone frags. From latter pottery came up (about 1/2 basket) much of which looked to be burnished red ware, several rim, body frags of bowls. O.K.? But also few frags of what seems Roman amphorae handles. Also 2 large unshaped alabaster frags. This all I saved in a basket - tagged. By end of this 1st day the workers said they had gone down w/ drill 5ms. They say they take samples every 1 m. They say the engineer (muhandis) comes every so often to check. It is a core sampling rig for bringing up samples.

FRIDAY 12/19/80: Visited the operation about noon. The muhandis had not yet come out to the operation. The workers thought they were down, as they said again 5-6 ms I saw one sample come up in the core sampler - it was mostly water w/ coagulated sand-limestone frags (small). The core sample is dumped out onto the surface sand, then scooped up by hand and placed on the low nearby cement topped limestone wall.

(OVER)

13/IX/80 I again visited the operation about noon. Still the muhandis had not been out need. to the workers. They said they were down 7 ms. Still getting water, limestone frags - sand. In the small piles of "samples" on the cement wall nearby I noticed one pile of small limestone frags had 1 granite frag - very small. The rig is all run by hand, the lifting of rods, etc. done by hand.

14/IX/80 Came to work at 7:30. Stopped by the operation. They still say they are down about 7 m. I watched as they brought up a core sample. It was a watery sand slurry w/ limestone frags. There was one small granite frag. included. From 8:00 - 2:00 I triangulated the position of the hole from our grid points extended along the front of the Sphinx and Valley Temples. I took an elevation on the surface of the hole from our beginning datum point further east on the N side of the paved road: the round cement (survey?) marker defined +10 m. It came to +10.39 - 10.41 m. Still the muhandis has not shown up once. The workers now say they are down about 10 ms. - guess timated on basis of 3 lengths of drill rod used. They have about 7-8 sample piles in the cement wall. The 3 last samples have each a single small granite fragment in otherwise small limestone frags. By end of day (5:00-5:30) I watched 2-3 core samples brought up. When the men jerk the line to pound the sampler cylinder down into the hole (about 30 cm diameter) there is a solid sounding thud at bottom of hole. The cylinder brings up much water, sand slurry (from upper part of hole?) and limestone frags. These are irregular natural looking frags - do not appear splintered w/ fresh breaks as though from breaking gebel by drill. Some look almost like diorite w/ a black speckled appearance - but likely discolored limestone. The reis of crew wonders if he is in gebel because the going is very tough. (Ma'ish fida he says).

15/IX/80 Stopped by operation in morning. The men say they are still down 9 m. (3 lengths of pipe 3 m each w/ last one protruding from surface). I watched them bring up a sample of sand-water slurry and more of limestone frags as last night. In pile of just previous sample there was one RW body shard. If that came up it would be hard to see if they were into gebel. (I actually poked this up off ground at base of cement wall on which sampler are kept. It was wet as though freshly up w/ wet sand on it. Considering the carelessness of the sampling, this could be contamination).

2:30 PM Reis says they have 5 sections of casing down in the hole now. I watched while the 5th was lowered (by turning press) down into hole. It sank fairly easy. The reis says it goes much better now. Reason: they are in a kind of grey sand-clay mix. Samples for last 2 ms. or so are globs of this grey compound which looks much like modern cement. The muhandis was out for 1st time at 10:00. I missed him. Noticed the granite frags., sherds seem to be missing from the earlier sample piles.

16/IX/80 Throughout day the workers maintain they are at 15 m. until about 5:00 when some assist to muhandis is there and says they are at 16 m. They are still getting dark grey clay but at 5:00 they brought up more limestone frags. with it.

17/IX/80 In morning at 8:00, I watched a core sample brought up. Much water w/ grey cement-colored slurry. However there was now a finer gravel mix in of small non-limestone pebbles.

- ⑥ SANDY-CLAY (Grey)
- ⑦ CONCENTRATED GREY CLAY
- ⑧ GREY CLAY W/ LIMESTONE FRAGS. 15 m.
- ⑨ GREY CLAY SLURRY W. NON-LIMESTONE GRAVEL. 16 m.

18/IX/80 Did not stop out to drill rig in morning. At 12:10 Inspectors Hassan and Ibrahim came to get me from work down in Rump passage. The muhandis was out at the rig: TAHIM SALAMA, 12 Saraya of Gezira, (809005). We talked about the SRI drilling. Told him I could put his drill hole on a map and section w/ Sphinx. As we talked the men were stamping the eye (I) beam on bottom. It hit hard w/ a thud. Because of last samples w/ grey clay - limestone frags. and the hardness of the bottom, they all thought they were on bottom-bedrock. As we stood there they pulled the I Beam out of the hole. Wedged into the slot in its end, red against the pale blue sky, was a big chunk of granite (which surprised us all). It was about 15 x 15 cm, and looked like it could be a crude corner piece. A big argument ensued between Inspector Ibrahim and the smaller muhandis from Min.-15 of Irrigation because Ibrahim wanted to take it to Taftish. (All this after I explained the granite cultural definitely - not natural). Ibrahim did take the fragment to Inspectorate. Some minutes later the core sampling cylinder was brought up and dumped out. It was water, grey slurry, and small granite particles throughout (disintegrated granite). Muhandis Fahim said he had to get to his office to report this as "very important." The drilling operation was suspended.

⑩ GRANITE